

First records of *Poltys monstrosus* Simon, 1897 (Araneae: Araneidae) from South Africa

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ABSTRACT: *Poltys monstrosus* Simon, 1897, a species described from Sierra Leone, has for the first time been reported from Mozambique, Swaziland, Zimbabwe and South Africa. The species is recognised by the abdomen that are thick and broadly flattened at the top. They are nocturnally active, building finely meshed orb webs at night and removing them around dawn. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Poltys* C.L. Koch, 1843 is represented by 42 species, of which nine are known from Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025). *Poltys* is a distinctive araneid genus recognised by a combination of widely separated lateral eyes and a pear-shaped carapace, where the “stalk” of the pear is an eye tubercle. Adult males are small and do not make webs, while the females are medium to large spiders. However, *Poltys* has an unexpectedly wide intra-specific variation in abdominal shape (Smith, 2003), suggesting that this plasticity may serve as a camouflage strategy against visually hunting predators like birds and wasps. In one group, the abdomens are rod-shaped and highly elongated, resembling twigs and in the other, the abdomens are thick and broadly flattened at the top, resembling dead buds, fruit or galls. The shape of the abdomen can vary among individuals within a species. Males are very small compared with females, and their abdomens are usually slightly extended oval.

They are nocturnally active, building finely meshed orb webs at night and removing them around dawn (Figs 1 & 2). The spiders are cryptically camouflaged, and during the day, they hide motionless on vegetation with their legs drawn tightly around their bodies (Fig. 6). Just the median eyes, which are situated on the anterior of the eye tubercle, are visible when they protrude between the legs. In this position, they often resemble part of a dead twig, a gall or a broken piece of wood.

Previously, only *Poltys furcifer* Simon, 1881, was known from South Africa. It is a species with a wide distribution across Africa. In 2014, the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) identification service received a photo of a spider with a broad, flattened abdomen that could not be identified at that time. It was only in 2024 when a similar species was identified from material sampled from the Fountain Hill Estate in KwaZulu-Natal that it was recognized as a *Poltys* species. The specimen was compared with the descriptions of other African *Poltys* species, and it keyed out as *P. monstrosus* Simon, 1897.

The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

TAXONOMY

Poltys monstrosus Simon, 1897

Poltys monstrosus Simon, 1897: 480 (Df)

Description: Female 10 mm. Body dull coloured, abdomen and legs densely covered with greyish-white setae (Fig. 2). Carapace pear-shaped; thoracic area with a very deep semicircular groove; ocular tubercle broad and obliquely inclined; carapace dark brown, smooth except for a broad band of setae stretching from fovea to eye region

Figures 1–2. *Poltys monstrosus*. 1. Female in orb web at Boesmansmond in the Eastern Cape (Mark Galpin). 2. Female in web at Blaauwberg Nature Reserve, Cape (Heather and Andrew Hodgson).

and clypeus (Fig. 3). Eyes: posterior lateral eyes are well separated from the anterior lateral eyes; median eyes closely grouped on anterior edge. Abdomen is large, barely longer than wide, covering the thoracic area; anterior margin rounded and furnished with rather small tubercles; three paired median tubercles are twinned,

Figures 3–5. *Poltys monstrosus*. 3–4. Female from Riebeeck West (Cecile Roux). 5. Female from Mbuluzi Game Reserve, Eswatini (Phil White).

with a few others slightly larger, and many small lateral tubercles toward the rear on both sides (Figs 4 & 5); adorned with somewhat irregular transverse zones, pale brownish-fawn in colour, covered with short, curved, dirty-white or yellowish hairs. Ventrally, pale brownish with the anterior region slightly darker. Legs with femora black with a bluish tint (Figs 4 & 5); the rest of the legs are densely covered with setae and are irregularly banded; four anterior tibiae are strongly curved, bearing long ventral spines in regular groups of four, and numerous irregular spines on the inner surface, which become shorter and denser toward the apex. *Poltys monstrosus* resemble the type species *P. illepidus* C.L. Koch, 1843, known from Japan to Australia.

LIFESTYLE

They are nocturnally active, building finely meshed orb webs at night and removing them around dawn. During the day they take up position on vegetation with the legs pulled very closely to the body, resembling part of a dead twig, a gall or a broken piece of bark (Figs 6 & 7).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique (iNat), Sierra Leone, Swaziland (iNat), South Africa (iNat) and Zimbabwe (iNat).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: (Fig. 8)

Figure 8. Distribution records of *Poltys monstrosus* in South Africa. Showing the SANSAs distribution records of material housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the locations of iNaturalist “Research Grade” observations of *Poltys monstrosus* from <https://www.inaturalist.org> exported on 24 September 2025.

Figures 6–7. *Poltys monstrosus* female from Cumberland Nature Reserve (Sunčana Bradley).

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